

Beam Diagnostics for Cyclotrons

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A) basic physics: effects used for transversal profile measurement

B) diagnostics along the beam path

- ion source & injection line: matching the beam to cyclotron acceptance
emittance, profile, current
- injection, central region: beam shaping & current set, betatron oscillation alignment
current, rough profile, collimator currents
- acceleration: adjustment of magnetic field and RF fields
current, rough profile, bunch phase
- extraction: efficiency, beam parameters, stability
current, profile, longitudinal profile, emittance

C) machine protection & control of activation
loss monitors, collimator currents

beam properties

- current of full beam
- transverse position of full beam
- phase of bunch center
- transverse profile - projection
 - 2D
- transverse emittance - 1D
 - 2D
- longitudinal profile
- longitudinal emittance
- beam ion energy distribution

usage

- for machine safety
- permanently
- for tuning
- at setup
- for error search
- only at commissioning

familiar monitors

- current transformer (DCCT, ACCT), Faraday-cup
- beam position monitor (BPM capacitive or inductive coupling)
- phase probe (capacitive coupling)
- wire monitor, wire grid („harp“)
screen
- emittance measurement device (slit-slit/slit-grid/Allison/3 profile/Q-pole variation)
pepperpot

monitor properties

- resolution
- temporal resolution / rate
- destructive vs. non-destructive (loss of beam up time, machine activation)
- low current limit (sensitivity, noise)
- high current limit (thermal damage, outgassing/sputtering)
- life time (radiation damage/hardness)
- reliability, cost,

special „cyclotron environment“ for monitors, drives, cooling

- high magnetic field / stray field (particularly compact cyclotrons)
- little space (particularly compact cyclotrons)
 - compact monitors, no radiation shielding, nearby activated components,
RF nearby

how to spend only 45 minutes on the vast field of diagnostics of cyclotrons & their injection lines? (disclaimer)

- **focus** on measurement principles / monitors relevant for tuning & performance
nearly nothing about details / technical issues / the „art of construction“ / electronics
- examples are **only examples**:
most examples based on PSI machines, but
many different machines with different diagnostic needs
many other variants of diagnostics in operation worldwide for a long time
choice of references is subjective
- useful methods are usually **not new**: nearly everything is described in the 1960's to 1980's
and hidden somewhere in Proc. Int. Conf. on Cyclotrons and their Applications (ICCA)
Clark, ICIC1966, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/c66/papers/a-002.pdf>, Olivo, ICCA1975, p. 331-340
- **more information** on beam diagnostics (mostly not from cyclotrons):
JACoW, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/> (includes Proc. ICCA since 2001)
Forck, JUAS 2009, http://www-bd.gsi.de/conf/juas/juas_script.pdf
Wittenburg/Braun/Bravin et al. CAS 2008, <http://cas.web.cern.ch/cas/France-2008/Lectures/Dourdan-lectures.htm>
Wittenburg, HB2006, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/abdw06/PAPERS/TUAZ01.PDF>
Raich, DIPAC2005, http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d05/TALKS/ITMM01_TALK.PDF
Brandenburg et al., DIPAC03, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d03/papers/CT10.pdf>
Dölling, DIPAC2005, http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/d05/TALKS/ITTA02_TALK.PDF
• • •

effects used for transversal profile measurement

(depending on geometry also for full beam or beam halo,
also part of emittance measurement)

$$P_{in} = U_{beam} * I_{beam}$$

„direct“ temperature measurement of stopper block
 or of cooling water in&outlet (+ flow measurement)

- can be calibrated by ohmic heating
- thermoelements are radiation hard
- small influence of (low energy) stray particles

$$P_{in} = \text{wire mass} * \text{stopping power} * \text{beam current density}$$

[V A]
[kg]
[V m²/kg]
[A/m²]

indirect temperature measurement of wire (or foil)

- vibration resonance shift (very sensitive)

Arutunian, BIW08, <http://www.als.lbl.gov/biw08/papers-final/MOSTFA01.PDF>

- resistance
- light emission (non-linear)
- thermionic emission current (non-linear)

wire melting/evaporation? → energy balance

Liaw, Cameron, PAC2001, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/p01/PAPERS/WPAH120.PDF>

Sapinski, Kroyer, BIW08, <http://www.als.lbl.gov/biw08/papers-final/TUPTPF066.pdf>

Example: carbon fibre, diameter 33 um

- 2000 K reached at DC current density

2.3 uA/mm² for 1 MeV protons

13 10

82 100

- approx. 40x higher current density for flying wire
 (5 m/s, 10 mm beam diameter)

direct measurement of current of stopped beam fraction

- stopping material thick enough? → for protons projected range <http://physics.nist.gov/PhysRefData/Star/Text/PSTAR.html>
 → for ions e. g. <http://www.srim.org>, <http://geant4.cern.ch>
- signal altered by secondary electron emission at surface, SE energy mostly around 2 eV, yield >1 at low beam energies
 for absolute measurements: suppression with electrode at ~100 V (electrode not to be hit by beam!)
 or with permanent magnets → Faraday cup
 for most applications: better to let SE escape or to pull them away
- signal altered by stray particles (residual gas ions, external SE)
- with magnetic fields & beam space charge → path of SE or stray particles difficult to predict (ExB-drift, ...)
- if directly water cooled: at very small currents measurement can be disturbed by water conduction

secondary emission current, direct measurement

wires or strips
or full foil
(fill factor, thickness
→ destructive or „not“)

- at higher energies: ions not stopped,
signal only from SE

- optional pulling of SE by external electrodes or adjacent foils
(foils also block stray particles, filtering of high voltage needed)

- SE-yield depends on surface material
& structure & contamination,
ion species & energy

- SE-yield depends on irradiation history,
Titanium is good [Ferioli, Jung, DIPAC97, pp. 168-170](#)

- signal is very fast (<ps)
and linear (large dynamic range)

Kramer et al., DIPAC2007, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d07/papers/wepc03.pdf>

according to Badano et al., DIPAC03/07

<http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d03/papers/CT09.pdf>

<http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d07/papers/wepc20.pdf>

- ~non-destructive
- fast
- sensitive
- fragile foil? → careful venting of beam line

other variants:

Kruglov et al., Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A 441 (2000) 595-604

Shapira et al., Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A 454 (2000) 409-420

detection of scattered or secondary particles

- scattering at high and low energies
(at not too low energies ~according to Rutherford formula)
- creation of secondaries at higher energies
- very large dynamic range (if background radiation low)

Raich, DIPAC05,
http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d05/TALKS/ITMM01_TALK.PDF

instead of moving wire or grid

- light emission spectrum (to be compatible with light detector)
- decay time ns >s
- doped bulk anorganic material (ceramic, glass, crystal → rugged)
doped plastics
thin coating on metal (phosphor powders → fragile)
thin layer in plastic (intensifying screens, Kodak Lanex = P43)
- image broadening by light scattering → thin screen
- saturation, thermal damage, radiation hardness
→ for limited beam current

http://www.proxitronic.de/datasheets/20091001_ebv.pdf

Type	Composition	Light Emission			Decay Time		
		from	to	Maximum typically at	Color	Decay of Light Intensity	
P 43	Gd ₂ O ₂ S:Tb	360 nm	680 nm	545 nm	green	from 90 % to 10 % in 1 ms	from 10 % to 1 % in 1,6 ms
P 46	Y ₂ Al ₅ O ₁₂ :Ce	490 nm	620 nm	530 nm	yellow green	300 ns	90 μs
P 47	Y ₂ SiO ₅ :Ce,Tb	370 nm	480 nm	400 nm	blue white	100 ns	2,9 μs

<http://cas.web.cern.ch/cas/France-2008/Lectures/Bravin.pdf>

Jung et al., DIPAC03, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d03/papers/IT03.pdf>

Gütlich et al., DIPAC09, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d09/papers/tupb04.pdf>

Re et al. PAC2005, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/p05/PAPERS/RPAT002.PDF>

paper/Kapton foil coloration

- colouring by beam heating
- readout with scanner
- not linear

radiographic film

- like photographic film
- development needed

track-etch foil

- tracks in nitrocellulose
- etched
- counted

radiochromic film

- optical density increases with dose
- dose range 0.001 ... 100 Gy
- easy to use (no light sensitivity, no development)
- readout with flatbed scanner
- can be calibrated

<http://www.gafchromic.com/>
 Mumot et al., PTCOG46,
[http://ptcog.web.psi.ch/PTCOG46/May%2022,%202007,%20morning/\(22\)-\(5.22\)\(9.00\)M.Mumot\(Dose%20distribution%20measurements\).pdf](http://ptcog.web.psi.ch/PTCOG46/May%2022,%202007,%20morning/(22)-(5.22)(9.00)M.Mumot(Dose%20distribution%20measurements).pdf)

Optical Density - Dose Calibration Curve
 for a Gafchromic EBT film (lot # 36076-0021)
 irradiated with protons

Bues, PTCOG45, http://online1.ispcorp.com/_layouts/Gafchromic/content/presentech/pdf/14MBues.pdf

foil activation

- activation of metal or polyethylene foil (if ion energy above a few MeV)
- contact radiography to
 - a) imaging plate (semistable excitation) read-out with laser scanner (deexcitation observed with PMT) few $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ detectable, 50 μm resolution \rightarrow very large dynamic range
 - b) radiochromic film \rightarrow large dynamic range
- linear

Clarke et al., NIM A 585 (2008) 117-120
 Tamburella, Giles, NIM B 266 (2008) 4678-81

Avila-Rodriguez et al., Applied Radiation and Isotopes 67 (2009) 2025-2028

ionisation chamber

instead of moving wire

- signal enhanced by ion pair generation $\eta = \text{stopping power} * \text{gas density} * \text{gas length} / \text{energy per ion pair}$

	[eV m ² /kg]	[kg/m ³]	[m]	[eV]	
example: 10 MeV protons in 1 cm air	1400	4e6	1.2	0.01	34.23

stopping power: <http://physics.nist.gov/PhysRefData/Star/Text/PSTAR.html>

- saturation effects only at higher beam current densities, (but signal still increasing)
- charge collection time $t_{coll} = (\text{gap})^2 * (\text{high voltage})^{-1} * k^{-1}$
example: gap 10 mm, high voltage 300 V
mobility of air $k_{air} \sim 1.7 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ V}^{-1} \rightarrow t_{coll} = 2 \text{ ms}$
- faster if only electrons used for signal („Frisch-grid chamber“, nitrogen filled, $t_{coll} \sim \mu\text{s}$)
- low energy limit: penetration of window
example: 50 μm Ti \rightarrow protons of 2.8 MeV

Dölling, DIPAC05, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/accelconf/d05/PAPERS/TTTA02.PDF>
@ homogeneous proton irradiation of full chamber

proportional chamber

- signal additionally enhanced by electron avalanche amplification by $\sim 10^4$
- amplification dependent on beam current density \rightarrow non-linear
- gas flow needed

gas electron multiplier (GEM)

front: ionisation chamber

gas, e. g. Ar (70%) CO₂ (30%)

middle: 1-3 GEM foils

rear: strip pattern 1D or 2x 1D or pixels

- signal additionally enhanced by electron avalanche by $10^2 - 10^5$ depending of number of GEMs

- less discharges with more GEMs
- amplification not dependent on beam current density
→ linear (at not too high current densities)
- radiation hard
- gas flow needed

electron avalanche
in high electric field
in holes

pictures from Gas Detectors Development Group, CERN, <http://gdd.web.cern.ch/GDD/>

The first external cyclotron beam, obtained on March 26, 1936. The glow arises from the ionization of the air by the 5.8 MeV deuterons.

http://imglib.lbl.gov/LBNL_Res_Revs/RR_online/81F/81fhp2.html

in air: deuterons stopped after half a meter

↓
scaled by 10^{-9} in pressure (10^{-6} mbar)

in residual gas:

distance earth – moon (i. e. non-destructive)

very faint glow

beam induced fluorescence

picture from Forck, JUAS2009

- detectors

ICCD or EMCCD

Becker et al., BIW08, <http://www-bd.gsi.de/uploads/paper/TUPTPF054.pdf>
Jung, DIPAC99, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d99/papers/CT12.pdf>

multichannel PMT

Plum et al., LHC Emittance Workshop (2000), see below
Dietrich et al., EPAC08, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/e08/papers/tupc022.p>

scanning PMT

Rezzonico et al., Rev. Sci. Instrum. 67(1996)1246-8
Joho et al., PAC1985 http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/p85/PDF/PAC1985_2666.PDF
Chamberlin et al. PAC1981 http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/p81/PDF/PAC1981_2347.PDF

TV camera

- cross sections energy dependent (Bethe-Bloch) → easier at low energy

Plum et al., Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A 492 (2002) 74-90
Plum et al., LHC Emittance Workshop (2000),
<http://emittanceworkshop.web.cern.ch/EmittanceWorkshop/Slides%20M.Plum/GSPM.pdf>

- spectral components

Becker et al., DIPAC09, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d09/papers/tupb02.pdf>
Ausset et al. EPAC02, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/e02/PAPERS/THPRI066.pdf>

- distortion & limited dynamic range by

background radiation, delayed deexcitation (in helium gas) & reflections

residual gas ions (with external fields)

1D-detector for residual gas ions
 (strip pattern & current measurement
 or MCP + CCD or ...)

- profile broadened by beam space charge (improved by vertical magnetic field & detecting electrons)
- non-destructive but eventual beam space charge neutralisation disturbed by external electric field
- sensitive

Kamerdzhev, DIPAC09, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d09/papers/tupb12.pdf>

DeLuca, PAC69, http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/p69/PDF/PAC1969_0813.PDF

residual gas ions (with beam space charge field)

Dölling et al., DIPAC99, LINAC96,
ICIS97: Rev. Sci. Instrum.69 (1998) 1094-9

Arauzo et al., NIMA 461 (2001) 111-114

- beam ion distribution creates residual gas ions & accelerating potential
- a positive beam potential depth of at least a few V is required
- analytical solution for charge density distribution of round non-neutralized beams
- non-destructive
- distortion of signal by charging of surfaces & stray magnetic fields

Dölling, DIPAC99,
<http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d99/papers/CT02.pdf>

electron beam probe

Gross et al, EPAC1990,
http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/e90/PDF/EPAC1990_0806.PDF

„re-invented“ several times:

Garscadden et al., J. Electron. Contr. 9 (1960) 473

Harp et al., Rev. Sci. Instrum. 36 (1965) 960

Shiloh et al., Rev. Sci. Instrum., 54 (1983) 46

Shestak et al., Triumf Design Note TRI-DN-87-36 (1987)

Prabir et al., Rev. Sci. Instrum. 76 (2005) 023301

and many others

- beam space charge potential deflects transversal electron beam
- deflection depending on impact parameter is measured
- analytical solution for charge density distribution of round beams (Abel inversion) [Stallings, J. Appl. Phys. 42 \(1971\) 2831](#)
- a positive beam potential depth of at least a few V is required
- non-destructive
- charging of surfaces and stray magnetic fields can be problematic
 - higher electron energy (→ less sensitivity) e. g. 75 keV [Aleksandrov et al., DIPAC09, http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d09/papers/tuoa03.pdf](#)
 - ions [Bossler et al., CERN/PS 2000-071, http://cdsweb.cern.ch/record/478698/files/ps-2000-071.ps.gz](#)

classification

configuration	effects usable for profile (or rough position) measurement in a cyclotron or its injection line	used A) for machine safety B) permanently C) for tuning D) at setup E) for error search F) only at commiss.	destructive	beam current range (assumed DC beam at 70 MeV, 10 mm diameter, to be determined more precisely)
heating of introduced solid matter				
in full beam	probe finger: direct temperature measurement	D E	yes	nA ... uA
beam edge	collimator: -"-	B C D	"no"	nA ... mA
wire	vibration resonance shift	C D E	~no	pA ... uA
wire	wire: resistance	C D E	~no	uA ... mA
in full beam	metal foil: thermal light emission/thermionic emission	A B F	~yes	uA
wire	wire: -"-	C D E	~no	-
direct beam current				
in full beam	probe finger: current of stopped beam fraction	D E	yes	nA ... uA
beam edge	collimator: -"-	A B C D	"no"	pA ... mA
wire	wire: -"-	C D E	~no	-
secondary particles from introduced solid matter				
wire	wire: secondary emission current, direct measurement	C D E	~no	pA ... mA
beam edge	foil: -"-	A B C D E	"no"	pA ... uA
in full beam	foil: secondary emission current, 2D-measurement	A B C D E	~no	pA ... uA
wire	wire + detection of scattered or secondary particles	C D E	~no	nA ... mA
in full beam	scintillating screens	C D E	yes	pA ... uA
"wire"	scintillating fibres + PMT	C D E	~no	<pA ... nA
changes to introduced solid matter				
in full beam	paper/Kapton darkening	F	yes	nA ... uA
in full beam	radiochromic film	F	yes	<pA ... nA
in full beam	foil activation analysis	F	yes	pA ... uA
secondary particles from introduced dense gases				
in full beam	ionisation chamber	(B) C D E	~yes	<pA ... uA
in full beam	proportional chamber	C D E	~yes	<<pA ... nA
in full beam	GEM	C D E	yes	<<pA ... nA
secondary particles from residual gas				
residual gas	beam induced fluorescence	A B C D E	no	mA ... >A
residual gas	residual gas ions (with external fields)	A B C D E	~no	uA ... A
residual gas	residual gas ions (with beam space charge field)	?	no	mA ... >A
beam space charge field				
"wire"	electron beam probe	B C D E	no	mA ... >A

diagnostics along the beam path

most examples from Inj. 2 cyclotron of PSI's high power proton facility

- part of "user lab" ~400 users/a
- targets M, E for meson production (graphite)
- spallation neutron source SINQ since 1998 (solid stainless steel + Pb target)
- test with liquid Pb-Bi target Megapie in 2006
- ultra cold neutron source UCN in 2010 (solid zircaloy + Pb target)
- operates 4800 h/a \approx 240 d/a \approx 9000 mAh/a
- ring cyclotron in operation since 1974 (100 μ A design goal \rightarrow 2.2 mA)

SINQ
Megapie

581 MeV
1.5 mA
0.9 MW

(dump)

collimators

Target E

Target M

8 s pulses to UCN
every 800 s

- high beam power
- separated sectors
 \rightarrow some space for diagnostics

Ring-cyclotron
590 MeV, 2.2 mA, 1.3 MW
CW (50 MHz)

CW

Inj. 2-cyclotron
72 MeV, 2.2 mA
160 kW
CW (50 MHz)

(0.06 mA for
isotope production)

Cockcroft-Walton
0.87 MeV protons
14 mA, 12 kW
CW

(dump)

injection line: matching the beam core to the cyclotron acceptance

- collimator current readout and interlock generation protects the machine
- beam positions and widths are needed for a proper alignment of the beam used at routine machine set-up (or for online centering)
- beam profiles give hints in case of problems
- needs reproducible but not very detailed results (preferably at low & full beam current)

Markovits, PAC 1987

- thermal slit scanner
(at 60 keV)
destructive

Olivo, ICCA1987 p. 519-22

- internal cooled copper block behind vertical slit
- measurement of water in-/outlet temperatures

profile monitors

wire scanner
(870 keV 12 mA
up to 15% DC)

Rezzonico, ICCA1987 p. 457-60

motor

worm gear
crank
con-rod

pendulum axis

wire or foil
(isolated)

-beam induced
fluorescence monitor
(870 keV full beam)

PMT + Lens scanned
non-destructive

- thermal slit scanner
(at 60 keV)
destructive

Olivo, ICCA1987 p. 519-22

- internal cooled copper block behind vertical slit
- measurement of water in-/outlet temperatures

profile monitors

-beam induced
fluorescence monitor
(870 keV full beam)

PMT + Lens scanned
non-destructive

- numerical simulations support the **design of the machine** and later modifications to it (this layout is based on a „simple“ envelope fit with linear space charge)
- the **emittance** of the ion source is needed in the **design phase** as input for a transport code

transversal emittance measurement

beam with emittance = 0
 (and no space charge)
 → no unordered moving particles → sharp focus

transversal emittance measurement

beam with emittance > 0
 (and no space charge)
 \rightarrow unordered particles directions \rightarrow beam broadens, no sharp focus

beam emittance determines if the beam can be focused through the beam pipe
(with the available focussing elements and not taking space charge into account)

emittance measurement is the measurement of the unordered particle directions or of the distribution in x - x' -space

direct emittance measurement methods

moving slit + grid

moving line of holes + screen

more information than slit + grid

Forek, JUAS2009, http://www-bd.gsi.de/conf/juas/juas_script.pdf

many other configurations (pepperpot, Allison scanner, ...)

3 profile method

Q-pole variation method

Braun, CAS2008, <http://cas.web.cern.ch/cas/France-2008/Lectures/Braun-Emittance.pdf>

- „moving the beam instead of moving the monitor“
- more difficult to exercise with high power beams

information input is only 3 beam widths
 → less information than direct measurements

emittance measurement by all the monitors in the beam line (with quadrupoles & dipoles in between)

- input: magnet currents & beam width from profile monitors
- envelope fit (over-determined) by „simple“ transport calculation (matrices) including linear space charge → emittance

- needs reproducible but not very detailed results (preferably at full beam current)
- useful for machines which accelerate different particles and need frequently adapted beam optics

profiles measured at 13% DC
space charge neutralisation ~0.5 for good fit
→ $\epsilon = 6 \pi \text{ mm mrad}$ @870 keV

PSI Graphic Transport by U. Rohrer includes linear space charge
download from http://people.web.psi.ch/rohrer_u/index.html

injection, central region: current set & beam shaping, betatron oscillation alignment

- current set with collimator

- beam shaped with collimators (collimators cooled, no activation below 2 MeV)

- machine protection by collimator readings

Injector 2
central region

- horizontal adjustment
(collimator, trim coil,
movable inflector dipole)
- vertical adjustment
(collimator, deflector,
inflector dipole)
- horizontal collimator
(with current measur.)
- vertical collimator
(with current measur.)
- diff.-integral probe
phase probe
- stopper
(with current measur.)

- current measured with stopper

- injection efficiency from comparison with Faraday cup or DCCT in injection line
(less critical in this case: enough beam, no activation below 2 MeV)

Injector 2
central region

- horizontal adjustment
(collimator, trim coil,
movable inflector dipole)
- vertical adjustment
(collimator, deflector,
inflector dipole)
- horizontal collimator
(with current measur.)
- vertical collimator
(with current measur.)
- diff.-integral probe
phase probe
- stopper
(with current measur.)

- beam „positions“ at full current: only from **collimator** currents, at low current: from **radial probe**
- vertical centering with **vertical adjustments**
- horizontal betatron oscillations around the **centered path** adjusted with **horizontal adjustments**

Injector 2
central region

- horizontal adjustment
(collimator, trim coil,
movable inflector dipole)
- vertical adjustment
(collimator, deflector,
inflector dipole)
- horizontal collimator
(with current measur.)
- vertical collimator
(with current measur.)
- diff.-integral probe
phase probe
- stopper
(with current measur.)

acceleration: adjustment of magnetic field and RF fields

phase probes

full beam
(2300 uA)

- horizontal adjustment
(trim coils,
electrostatic septum,
septum magnet)
- accelerating gaps
- phase probes,
time structure probe
- radial probes

10 radial „spokes“ of bunches
aligned to pass accelerating gaps synchronously

phase probes

full beam
(2300 uA)

MIF - Phasenmessung Nr. 2846 - 09

Mini-Save

MIF-Phasenmessung

Datum: 2009.09.30 Zeit: 11:43:27

Trimmspul-Werte

	Messung	Fit-Wert
T11	-10	
T12	350	
T13	-882	-850
T14	-1134	-1200
T15	-1200	-1150
T16	-808	-800
T17	-63	-50
T18	383	300
T19	882	850
T110	1086	950
T111	-600	-650
AIHS	1948	2001

MXC1	2298.40	uA
AIHS	54000	DAC
CI1V	49280	DAC
CI2V	39240	DAC
CI3V	51337	DAC
CI4V	13650	DAC
CIPHFT	1700	DAC
SWV11X	1150	DAC
TIK	40	DAC
TI1DIFF	210	DAC
AWDY	1.59	mm
AWD	40815	DAC
CWBV	1160	DAC
CWBPH	41	DAC
CWBPHF	2442	DAC
CWB3V	240	DAC
CWB3PHF	2267	DAC
MXF1	100.02	Grad
OFFSET	0.49	Grad
Turn DAC	81.42	
Turn ADC	81.17	

M. Humbel, PSI

„isochronism“: 10 radial „spokes“ of bunches aligned to pass acceleration gaps synchronously from phase probes

- correction of (drifting) main field (recommended in this example)
- recommendation of better trim coil settings

„frequent tuning procedure“

- 9 pick-ups in Injector 2 cyclotron and 13 pick-ups in ring cyclotron
- uses the second harmonic (101MHz), phase measurement with an I-Q down converter
- RF contribution by "beam-off" measurement subtracted
- beam current 0.1 μ A ... 2 mA
- precision $\pm 0.5^\circ$ (over the whole dynamic range of 80 dB), phase range $\pm 90^\circ$
- bandwidth 5 Hz ... 500 Hz dependent on beam current

- variant: improved sensitivity by intensity modulation of the beam

Brandenburg et al., DIPAC03, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d03/papers/PT12.pdf>

long radial probe

- only for few uA beam
- finding the beam and „pulling“ it to greater radii at commissioning or „error search“

horizontal adjustment
(trim coils,
electrostatic septum,
septum magnet)

accelerating gaps

phase probes,
time structure probe

radial probes

Rezzonico, ICCA1987 p. 457-60

long radial probe

only 1 uA beam

RIL1 Messung Nr. 1-92 Bereich: 511mm bis 1511mm

RIL 1-Innenmessung, 4% gepulst Datum: 2-MAR-92 Zeit: 04:22:44

Pseudo Tomographie (skaliert mit 1.0)

Mini-Save

EWBRV	810.77kV	DAC
ESEX	59.96kV	DAC
AIHS	55800	DAC
TI1	2268	FEIN
TI2	1800	DAC
TI3	2000	DAC
TI4	-450	DAC
TI5	-450	DAC
TI6	-450	DAC
TI7	-400	DAC
TI8	-300	DAC
TI9	350	DAC
TI10	700	DAC
TI11	250	DAC
TI12	300	DAC
CI1V	52000	DAC
CI2V	0	DAC
CI3V	47410	DAC
CI4V	0	DAC
CIPHFT	1600	DAC
AWDX	1.60mm	DAC
TI1DIFF	500	DAC
TIK	-1000	DAC
KIP2	405.38mm	DAC
KIP4L	598.06mm	DAC
KIP4R	611.02mm	DAC
AWD7	0.01mm	DAC
AWD	61340	DAC
EIV1V	-100	DAC
EIV2V	40	DAC
A	-1.07mm	DAC
B	0.63mm	DAC
C	0.19mm	DAC
D	-2.10mm	DAC
Turn DAC	91.87	DAC

M. Humbel, PSI

control of vertical centering & horizontal betatron oscillation (here now only at commissioning or error search)

acceleration: adjustment of magnetic field and RF fields

R. Dölling, Beam Diagnostics for Cyclotrons, ECPM2009

long radial probe

only 1 uA beam
only vertical
finger displayed

RIL 1 Messung Nr. 67 - 07

Bereich: 515mm bis 3514mm

Datum: 2007.04.25 Zeit: 17:37:14

Strahlqualitaet

Turn DAC 80.65
Turn ADC 79.94

Radien von Finger Nr. 2

538.00	640.00	682.80	750.80	811.80	869.20	923.20	977.80	1028.80	1075.40
1123.40	1173.00	1218.00	1262.80	1307.60	1352.20	1395.20	1437.80	1480.40	1522.40
1562.20	1604.60	1645.80	1685.40	1725.60	1764.80	1803.00	1841.40	1880.40	1918.40
1953.80	1991.00	2026.40	2062.40	2099.20	2133.00	2169.00	2203.60	2237.80	2270.40
2305.80	2369.60	2402.20	2434.80	2467.20	2499.80	2527.80	2558.20	2589.80	2617.00
2650.20	2679.20	2710.00	2737.60	2766.80	2796.20	2824.60	2851.80	2880.00	2906.00
2932.40	2959.80	2987.40	3012.60	3046.80	3080.00	3111.00	3142.20	3167.40	3191.40
3218.60	3240.40	3288.60	3311.40	3355.20	3399.20	3479.80			

Mini-Save

EWBRV	811.87	kV
EVEX	60.00	kV
AIHS	55844	DAC
AIHS	2910	DAC
TI1	140	DAC
TI2	888	DAC
TI3	-600	DAC
TI4	-975	DAC
TI5	-1043	DAC
TI6	-800	DAC
TI7	-150	DAC
TI8	243	DAC
TI9	788	DAC
TI10	1043	DAC
TI11	43	DAC
C11V	49290	DAC
C12V	38804	DAC
C13V	51787	DAC
C14V	38804	DAC
CIPHFT	1720	DAC
AWDX	1.98	mm
TI1DIFF	2330	DAC
TIK	-1000	DAC
KIP2	411.65	mm
KIP4L	402.83	mm
KIP4R	623.31	mm
AWDY	1.98	mm
AWD	60990	DAC
EIV1V	-340	DAC
EIV2V	0	DAC

M. Humbel, PSI

counting the turns
at beam development

alternative for not separated turns:

- measurement of beam noise (from ion source)
before and after the cyclotron
- cross correlation → time of flight

Loyer et al., PAC1985,

http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/p85/PDF/PAC1985_1938.PDF

extraction: efficiency, beam parameters, stability

electrostatic septum for extraction

D. Götz, PSI

septum foils between the last 2 turns

as few as possible beam should hit the foils in order to prevent beam loss

extraction probe 2

full beam
(2300 μ A)
only vertical
finger displayed

RIE2 Messung Nr. 23 - 09

Bereich: 3199mm bis 3349mm Datum: 2009.09.30 Zeit: 11:40:49

RSP [mm]	3233.5	3249.1	3270.3	3318.1
4 σ	13.7	14.5	14.2	14.3

Strahlqualitaet

BRV	14.19	mm
Verlust	54.800	nA
Turn DAC	81.62	
Puls 1 :	1.00	

Zentrierung

RO	3301.94	mm
DR	23.25	mm
E	-3.08	
F	4.75	

Mini-Save

EWBRV	44120	DAC
CIPHFT	1900	DAC
MXC1	2302.20	μ A
MWC2	10.48	mA
KIDE	-0.01	μ A
KXA 11	0.13	μ A
AIHS	1948	FEIN
KIP2	399.02	mm
RIL 2	534.69	mm
KIP4L	605.77	mm
KIP4R	614.84	mm
T11	-10	DAC
SWV11X	1150	DAC
AWDX	1.10	mm
TIK	40	DAC
T11DIFF	210	DAC
C11V	49280	DAC
C12V	39240	DAC
C13V	51337	DAC
C14V	33550	DAC
CIPHFT	1900	DAC

Rezzonico et al., BIW1994, AIP Conf. Proc. 333 p. 398-404

horizontal betatron oscillation tuned for

- large separation of last turn at extraction elements
- nearly 100% extraction efficiency = low losses

„set-up & beam development procedure“

extraction probe 1

full beam
(2300 μ A)
only vertical
finger displayed

RIE1 Messung Nr. 420 - 09

Bereich: 3198mm bis 3397mm Datum: 2009.09.30 Zeit: 11:35:01

RSP [mm] 3209.8 3242.2 3262.8 278.7 3311.8 3330.5 3348.5
4 σ 11.0 12.1 12.7 12.1 11.5 12.0 13.2

Strahlqualität

BRAY	12.08	mm
Verlust	72.650	nA
Turn DAC	81.42	
Puls 1 :	1.00	
Beam	100.00	% on DC
Res. 2+4	150.00	MHz ein

Zentrierung

Ro	3354.21	mm
DR	22.99	mm
E	-1.97	mm
F	4.40	mm

Mini-Save

EWRV	44120	DAC
CIPHFT	1900	DAC
MXC1	2305.50	μ A
MWC2	10.48	mA
KXA1	0.16	μ A
AIHS	1950	%
KIP2	398.94	mm
MITR	50.71	%
RIL2	534.69	mm
CVBV	1140	DAC
CVBPH	41	DAC
CVBPHF	2443	DAC
CVB3V	240	DAC
CVB3PHF	2268	DAC
TI1	-10	DAC
TI2	350	DAC
MI6	2.226	nA
SWV11X	1150	DAC
AWDX	1.11	mm
TIK	40	DAC
TI1DIFF	210	DAC
CI1V	49280	DAC
CI2V	38240	DAC
CI3V	51332	DAC
CI4V	33550	DAC

Rezzonico et al., BIW1994, AIP Conf. Proc. 333 p. 398-404

practically done by adjusting sine & cosine at the other extraction probe

(\rightarrow groups of three turns form
 \rightarrow number of turns should be changed only by n times 3)

„tuning, set-up & beam development procedure“

extraction probe 1

only vertical
finger displayed

RIE1 Messung Nr. 132 - 02

Bereich: 3198mm bis 3397mm

Datum: 18-MAR-02

Zeit: 07:50:22

RSP [mm]

4σ

Strahlqualiaet

BRV	11.88 mm
Verlust	48.88 nA
Turn DAC	85.81
Puls 1 :	1.00
Beam	100.00% on DC
Res. 2+4	150.00MHz ein

Zentrierung

Ro	3356.88 mm
DR	22.50 mm
E	-1.88 mm
F	8.88 mm

Mini-Save

EWBRV	58982	DAC
CIPHFT	1650	DAC
MXC 1	1090.80 uA	
MWC 2	12.28 mA	
KXA 11	-0.68 uA	
AHS	24.40 FEIN	
KIP2	38.88 mm	
MITR	21.88 %	
RIL 2	521.53 mm	
KIP4L	800.18 mm	
KIP4R	610.78 mm	
CWBV	1230	DAC
CWBPH	43	DAC
CWBPHF	1965	DAC
TI 1	299	DAC
TI 2	600	DAC
SWV 11X	1040	DAC
AWDX	1.53 mm	
TIK	-2400	DAC
TI 10IFF	400	DAC
CI 1V	49500	DAC
CI 2V	27800	DAC
CI 3V	48820	DAC
CI 4V	27800	DAC

M. Humbel, PSI

developing valley for extraction elements
 unchanged by beam current variation
 (accomplished by cutting the beam single-
 sided with a collimator in the machine center)
 → good extraction efficiency at all currents

time structure probes

- measure longitudinal and radial density distributions of the beam bunches (averaging over many bunches)
- arrival time of scattered protons compared to RF reference (discriminator & Time-to-Ampl. Converter & Multi-Channel-Analyzer)
- resolution incl. electronics ~31 ps fwhm (determined from correlation between detectors A, B)
- variant: scintillator in radial probe head

Chautard et al., ICCA2001, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/c01/cyc2001/paper/P4-17.pdf>

data used for layout of buncher between cyclotrons

simple estimate of time resolution of detector B

PMT transit time spread (TTS)	250 ps	(R7400)
scintillator response	1360 ps	(NE111)
path in scintillator	400 ps	

$$dt = 1.2 \sqrt{\frac{250^2 + 1360^2 + 400^2}{5500}} = 23 \text{ ps fwhm}$$

moving bunches as seen from above
(comoving square 10x10 mm
10 mm = 90 ps = 1.6° RF)

at cyclotrons with high extraction efficiency (mostly high power machines):

- a direct measurement of the small current difference is difficult
- loss monitors are calibrated with a deliberately lost small known beam current
(which is measured beforehand with a stopper in the following beam line)
→ loss monitor readings at normal operation can be converted to lost beam current
- extraction efficiency = $1 - \text{lost beam current} / \text{measured beam current}$
- here this number is only of academical interest: the measured loss itself is important

at cyclotrons with extraction efficiency significantly <1
(and usually no turn-separation at extraction):

- measurement of the beam current at the machine center and after extraction
- e. g. with a long radial probe
- “integral probe”

Accel / Varian, Geisler et al., ICCA2007,
<http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/c07/PAPERS/9.PDF>

example: radial probe of PSI's medical cyclotron:

at low & high energies: full beam stopped

→ extraction efficiency = $I_{\text{highE}} / I_{\text{lowE}}$

at medium energies: part of the beam scattered & lost
(due to probe geometry)

- probe measures turn density
- radial betatron oscillations visible
- information on horizontal beam centering

horizontal betatron oscillations decreased to zero since anyway no turn separation at extraction

comparison to simulation: Schippers et al. ICCA2004, http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/c04/data/CYC2004_papers/21A3.pdf

[insertion: acceleration: adjustment of magnetic field and RF fields]

differential probe head

commissioning radial probe of PSIs medical cyclotron

Accel/Varian, Timmer et al., ICAP2006, <http://bel.gsi.de/icap2006/PAPERS/TUPPP01.PDF>

- beam measured on vertical wire (and stopped at latest on stopper block)
- probe measures radial turn profile (red) (turns in center region still separated)
- B-field trimmed until turn separation (blue points) varies gently (as theoretical prediction: green line)

Accel / PSI

screen foil

commissioning of PSI's medical cyclotron

- grazing beam pass over screen foil (foil similar to the one shown here)
- viewed with external CCD camera through window (turn 3 – 8 visible)

view through window

(turn 3 – 8 visible)

Accel / PSI

at high currents:

- DC/AC current transformers

Denard, CAS2008, <http://cas.web.cern.ch/cas/France-2008/Lectures/Denard.pdf>
Webber, Proc. AccApp'07 p. 145-151

- resonant cavity Reimann, Ruede, NIM 129 (1975) 53-58

at low currents:

- Cryogenic Current Comparator

Vodel et al., DIPAC2007, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d07/papers/webp30.pdf>

- thin SEMs or ionisation chambers (scattering!)

example:

ionisation chamber behind PSIs medical cyclotron

Dölling et al., Proc. AccApp'07 p. 152-159

measures current fluctuations from the internal ion source

Schippers et al., ICCA2007, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/c07/PAPERS/300.PDF>

6 μm titanium foils
soldered to
thick-film coated
ceramic frames

thin SEM or ionisation chamber behind PSIs medical cyclotron

used for proton beam 250 MeV

IC: in a N_2 filled box
with thin Ti-windows
signal amplified by 43
thermal limit: 1 μA beam

SEM: in vacuum
signal „amplified“ by 0.053
microphonics

machine protection & control of activation

(an issue for high current / continuously operating machines)

machine protection from high power beams

- melting of beam line/cyclotron components by missteered beam
→ 2...300 days shut down for replacement/repair/remanufacturing
(no spare parts for many components, many parts difficult to reach
sometimes lack of documentation/drawings/exact dimensions)
- time t_{melt} depending on beam diameter/energy
- fast interlock generation needed (<1 ms)

collimators

- with current readout

injection into Ring cyclotron:
collimator and coil support destroyed
(defect of high level interlock module)

590 MeV, 2.2 mA, 1.3 MW, $t_{\text{melt}} = 10$ ms

loss monitors

here: ionisation chambers

- chamber signal linear in used range
- placed $\sim 0.1 \dots 1$ m from beam, fixed position for reproducibility
- useful at beam energies > 40 MeV \rightarrow proton range in steel > 3 mm
- ambient air filled, 300 V, gap = 1 cm, 2 litres
- also circular type around beam tube/cylindrical in shielding
- simple and reliable, radiation hard
- to consider for dose estimates:
scattering in forward direction,
shielding by components (!),
neutrons,
1 nA signal ~ 1.3 Gy/d

- radiation induced attenuation of optical fibers (range few kGy, position resolution ~1 m)

Wulf, Körfer, DIPAC09, <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/d09/papers/weoa01.pdf>

(Roughly) Estimated Sensitivities

linear in used range, very radiation hard

- Ionization chamber:** **70 μC/Gy**
 1 liter argon
 $S \approx \text{active mass} \cdot \text{charge per ionization energy} \approx V \cdot \rho \cdot e / E_{\text{ion}} \approx 1 \text{ l} \cdot 1.8 \text{ g/l} \cdot e / 26 \text{ eV}$
- Long ionization chamber:** **20 μC/Gy**
 1 meter length, 1 cm radius, argon
 $S \approx \text{active mass} \cdot \text{charge per ionization energy} \approx \pi r^2 \cdot L \cdot \rho \cdot e / E_{\text{ion}} \approx 314 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot 1.8 \text{ g/l} \cdot e / 26 \text{ eV}$
- PIN diode:** **6 μC/Gy**
 1 cm² surface, 100 μm depletion depth
 $S \approx \text{active mass} \cdot \text{charge per excitation energy} \approx A \cdot d \cdot \rho \cdot e / E_{\text{ion}} \approx 10 \text{ mm}^3 \cdot 2.3 \text{ g/cm}^3 \cdot e / 3.6 \text{ eV}$
- Secondary emission monitor:** **500 pC/Gy**
 100 cm² surface, 0.01 average secondary emission yield (SEY)
 $S \approx \text{surface} \cdot \text{SEY} \cdot \text{electron charge} \cdot \text{density of primaries per dose} \approx A \cdot \text{SEY} \cdot e \cdot (\rho / (dE/dx))$
 $\approx 100 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot 0.01 \cdot e \cdot 1 / (2 \text{ MeV} \cdot \text{cm}^2/\text{g})$
- Aluminum cathode electron multiplier:** **5 μC/Gy**
 10 cm² surface, 0.01 average secondary emission yield (SEY), tube gain 10⁵
 $S \approx \text{surface} \cdot \text{SEY} \cdot \text{electron charge} \cdot \text{density of primaries per dose} \cdot \text{gain} \approx A \cdot \text{SEY} \cdot e \cdot (\rho / (dE/dx)) \cdot G$
 $\approx 10 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot 0.01 \cdot e \cdot 1 / (2 \text{ MeV} \cdot \text{cm}^2/\text{g}) \cdot 10^5$
- PMT with organic scintillator:** **200 C/Gy**
 1 liter scintillator, 60% collection efficiency, 30% photocathode efficiency, tube gain 10⁵
 $S \approx \text{active mass} \cdot \text{photon yield per energy} \cdot \text{collection efficiency} \cdot \text{photocathode efficiency} \cdot \text{gain} \cdot \text{electron charge}$
 $\approx V \cdot \rho \cdot Y \cdot C \cdot P \cdot G \cdot e = 1 \text{ l} \cdot 1 \text{ g/cm}^3 \cdot 1 / (100 \text{ eV}) \cdot 0.6 \cdot 0.3 \cdot 10^5 \cdot e$
- Bare PMT (Čerenkov light):** **4 mC/Gy**
 10 cm² surface, 1 mm thick, 30% photocathode efficiency, tube gain 10⁵
 $S \approx \text{active volume} \cdot \text{density of primaries per dose} \cdot \text{photon yield per length} \cdot \text{photocath. efficiency} \cdot \text{gain} \cdot \text{electron charge}$
 $\approx A \cdot d \cdot \rho \cdot (\rho / (dE/dx)) \cdot Y \cdot P \cdot G \cdot e \approx 1 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot 1 / (2 \text{ MeV} \cdot \text{cm}^2/\text{g}) \cdot 260/\text{cm} \cdot 0.3 \cdot 10^5 \cdot e$
- PMT with Čerenkov fiber:** **2 μC/Gy**
 1 meter length, 100 μm radius, 2% collection efficiency, 30% photocathode eff., tube gain 10⁵
 $S \approx \text{active volume} \cdot \text{density of primaries per dose} \cdot \text{photon yield per length} \cdot \text{coll. eff.} \cdot \text{photoc. eff.} \cdot \text{gain} \cdot \text{electron charge}$
 $\approx \pi r^2 \cdot L \cdot \rho \cdot (\rho / (dE/dx)) \cdot Y \cdot C \cdot P \cdot G \cdot e \approx 31 \text{ mm}^3 \cdot 1 / (2 \text{ MeV} \cdot \text{cm}^2/\text{g}) \cdot 260/\text{cm} \cdot 0.02 \cdot 0.3 \cdot 10^5 \cdot e$

linear even at very high dose rate, very radiation hard

Radiation damage problematic!

very sensitive

only for relativistic particles (β>0.68)

Flexible gain → linearity and calibration problematic!

but profile monitors can contribute to improvements of design of an already running machine:

- if detailed numerical simulations (including beam halo, scattering at collimators, 3D-poisson solver, space charge neutralisation) lead to a better understanding of the losses
- then detailed proposals can be made for an improved machine layout and beam shaping by collimators (in the environment of a production machine such changes are nearly impossible on a trial & error basis)
- such simulations need a realistic input on the beam phase space distribution
- this input can be generated (as part of the simulation) from the detailed information from profile monitors with high dynamic range
- the simulations can also be calibrated by introducing additional beam scattering with wire scanners and observing the downstream profiles and loss monitor readings

detection of beam ions scattered ~ 20 m upstream by a 33 mm carbon fibre placed in the beam with two vertical wire scanners in front of the Ring-cyclotron (losses in Ring-cyclotron increased $\sim 40\%$)